

ACCESSIBILITY, CULTURAL EXPERIENCE AND COMMUNICATION FOR A SHARED HERITAGE

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Abstract

Our cultural heritage is an expression of the tangible, intangible and now also digital creations of the communities living in a territory, and access to this heritage is only possible if the heritage becomes an inclusive and participatory tool, if the cultural site becomes an educational site, an agora where all actors can interact and develop knowledge and skills. In this panorama, the "digital dimension" is both a challenge and a key to understanding the present in order to try to imagine the scenarios of tomorrow.

Keywords: Heritage, Architecture, Design, Accessibility, Digital.

1 INTRODUCTION

The issue of accessibility to cultural heritage has been of growing interest at the global level in recent decades, as evidenced by the role of accessibility as a requirement of the UNESCO World Heritage List. First of all, recalling art. 3 of the Italian Constitution, which has addressed the issue of accessibility since 1948, declaring that "the Republic has the task of removing economic and social obstacles which, by limiting the freedom and equality of citizens, prevent the full development of the human person and the effective participation of all workers in the political, economic and social organisation of the country", but also the Code of Cultural Heritage and Landscape, recently updated in 2019, and the series of guidelines drawn up by the Ministry for Cultural Heritage and Activities (now MiC) "to promote the best public enjoyment of the Italian cultural heritage [...] consider accessibility as a priority action to be placed at the basis of any conservation and enhancement intervention", the importance that the issue of accessibility, aimed at a wider user base, assumes in the revaluation of the architectural and landscape heritage in all its expressions is becoming increasingly clear (Agostiano et al. 2008).

In this context, Italy has been addressing this issue since 2009 with the creation of a specific Directorate General at the Ministry of Culture, whose objectives were merged in 2014 into the Directorate General for Museums, whose aim is to promote the development of culture by acting as an active player in the processes of creating services, activities and tools to satisfy users and increase the enjoyment of heritage for all citizens. In addition to these considerations, the establishment of 2018 as the European Year of Cultural Heritage by the Parliament and the Council of the European Union represents a further challenge to continue to look to the future and design in unique and precious places through the valorisation of the richness of the EU's cultural heritage (Cetorelli, Guido 2017).

In this perspective, it is increasingly important and necessary to reflect on the issue of accessibility to cultural sites, which is diminished in several dimensions, and on the individual and/or contextual interactions that could constitute an obstacle to their realisation. We are talking about tangible, intangible and digital barriers, or even material and immaterial, or even physical, sensory, cognitive, behavioural, technological, economic,

etc.: these are not absolute concepts, but inherent to a process of audience engagement aimed at achieving different levels of fruition for different user profiles (Manifesto of Culture Accessible to All, 2012).

It is therefore essential to see accessibility as a cultural perspective that can guarantee access and full enjoyment of places, stories and memories for everyone.

Such a wider access can now also make use of the new digital technologies, thus greatly extending the possibilities of enjoying our cultural heritage, also in the name of that intangible heritage which has already become a subject of international debate since the Burra Charter (1979), and above all in the implementation of the "right of access for all to culture", as indicated in the Faro Convention, recently ratified by Italy, which stresses the need to

"Promote measures to improve access to cultural heritage, especially for young and disadvantaged people, in order to increase awareness of its value, the need to preserve and conserve it and the benefits that can be derived from it (Art. 12)".

In line with current common orientations on cultural heritage, it is foreseeable that developments on the issue of accessibility will converge on that of use, increasingly opening up to an active role of citizens and communities in all stages of conservation and enhancement processes, from planning to management. In fact, there is a gradual shift from a kind of "exclusive" use, dominated by a top-down relationship with mostly passive and detached visitors, to a current, more inclusive trend, where people actively participate in the processes of knowledge, conservation and valorisation, through strategies that focus on bottom-up models and in accordance with the principles of Universal Design or Design for all.

These developments have enhanced the various facets of the concept of accessibility: in addition to the physical 'moment', two circumstances can be identified in the experience of accessibility, in which the intangible aspects are condensed: 'perceptual' accessibility, i.e. that which is mainly based on the mental perceptiveness and intellectual and educational background of the visitor/user, and 'appropriative' accessibility, in which an emotional feeling of 'connection with the heritage' is achieved, expressing the ability to interweave this feeling with one's personal and collective sphere.

2 THE ROLE OF DIGITAL IN RESEARCHING AND VALORISING CULTURAL HERITAGE

The 21st century and our daily lives are characterised by an evolutionary speed that forces us to acquire new literacies, to develop new multidisciplinary skills and to strengthen digital communication skills. In fact, we are living in a historical era in which most of our interactions are handled by electronic and IT tools, thus influencing many aspects of our daily lives that are increasingly marked by the predominant presence of technology.

This ongoing evolution of society has inevitable impacts, gradually changing the means of communication, the relationship with the cultural factor and the way we enjoy culture. In this sense, the so-called Digital Cultural Heritage represents a wider universe in which to experiment the integration between traditional humanistic knowledge and computer techniques and methodologies, initiating a path capable of developing valuable transversal skills to build an active participation in digital innovation processes and generate new models of knowledge, participation, management, exploitation and valorisation of our cultural heritage. It was this panorama that motivated and guided my research, which is still ongoing, and which started from a few simple questions. The first one was to inspire me to investigate the factors that hinder access to and enjoyment of cultural heritage.

If we take a broader view, it is easy to see that the cause of inaccessibility is not only the temporary or permanent disability of users. In addition to access and routes that are denied or restricted by the presence of architectural barriers, we must take into account several other forms of "inaccessibility" of sites; that is, we must take into account the fact that accessibility can be conditioned by the fragility of sites, limited or selective, for example, in the case of places that are difficult to access, and finally suspended - or definitively lost - in the case of damaged or destroyed sites and assets.

Moreover, it is not only architectural barriers that determine the accessibility of cultural heritage: the possibility of physically visiting the places and spaces where tangible heritage is materialised or where intangible heritage is contextualised is not always a sufficient condition to make it truly accessible. The accessibility of an item also depends on the ability to understand its meaning, especially when it is not easily interpretable.

In this respect, Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) offer the opportunity to improve and broaden the understanding of cultural heritage through various applications and tools. Virtual reconstructions, holograms and 3D models for cultural communication and entertainment, virtual exhibitions, "hyper-museums" with interactive applications and animations, virtual visits to inaccessible places, are now able to bring heritage content to a wide audience, including the younger generations, thanks to serious games and various other immersive and interactive experiences.

3 BUILDING AN INTEGRATED METHODOLOGICAL PROJECT APPROACH

In the light of new trends, which see the meaning of cultural heritage evolve from a typically patrimonial vision to one more linked to the concept of inheritance, accessibility becomes a necessary condition to guarantee the valorisation of the very essence of heritage, proposing it for open and continuous enjoyment over time. Historic urban contexts are stimulating laboratories in which to test these ideas and assess how heritage can become an important factor in the sustainable development and economic growth of the city, and at the same time an interesting research ground for innovative regeneration strategies. Focusing on the heritage-city interface, this research aims to develop a 'heritage-accessibility led' design approach to facilitate urban understanding and perception of the cultural heritage of sites and contexts, and to promote the link between the city and its strata. It is the combination of these two factors - 'physical' accessibility and understanding of cultural value - that determines the true 'permeability' of a historic site (Agostiano, Concas 2020; MiBACT 2017).

The subject of contemporary intervention in historic urban contexts, as fascinating as it is complex, encompasses, and even overlaps, multiple aspects of different disciplinary and cultural natures. Designing interventions on the existing is first and foremost a matter of knowledge, understanding and interpretation, and in this sense the contemporary architectural project, nourished by the necessary contaminations of technological innovation, assumes a strategic role in the broader debate on preservation/valuation and, more generally, old/new.

At this delicate interface, the so-called digital transition has triggered new ways of thinking, acting, interacting and communicating, participating in an evolutionary process of cultural heritage that can be used and explored in new ways. The emergence of digital tools and new environments inevitably raises new questions for research, and their intersection with historical contexts gives heritage an active role in the construction of the future and the project the task of becoming an interpreter of the continuous transformation of places and meanings. Conservation and transformation no longer seem to be antagonistic positions, but two activities that can coexist and guide choices with a realistic and flexible approach capable of taking into account the vastness and complexity of the variables at stake.

On the basis of these considerations, the applied field of research moves towards a theoretical and methodological fine-tuning of the declination of the accessibility requirement for the outdoor built environment of historic layouts, aiming at the recognition and enhancement of the urban architectural palimpsest through a series of transformative design strategies.

Three variables are studied as fundamental nodes of the project: the "layers of knowledge" that characterise the site to be enhanced; the users who interact with it and are at the same time the beneficiaries of the project; the tools whose use influences the quality of the process and at the same time orientates the intervention strategies towards the heritage. Contextual knowledge can ideally be divided into three macro-areas, relating to three dimensions of cultural heritage as defined by UNESCO.

More specifically:

1. Tangible: monuments, agglomerations and cultural sites
2. Intangible: art, traditions, cultural practices
3. Natural: landscape, territory, environment

This urban and territorial palimpsest can be interpreted and described by means of a series of tools that relate the aspects of conservation to overcoming architectural, sensory and perceptual barriers, promoting functional, spatial and cultural usability, and seeking design solutions that guarantee the best conditions of comfort and safety for the third variable considered: the users.

These could be defined as rightholders rather than stakeholders, according to a participatory rights-based approach [ICOMOS 2014] in line with the philosophy of UNESCO and the principles of the Faro Convention,

who become actors in the urban scene. Starting from the necessary construction of a user map that lists different categories of users, such as the local population, students, researchers, specialists and tourists - distinguished by culture, age and physical conditions - the network of relationships activated between the different nodes (layer-user-tool) can lead to the definition of potential, dynamic and interactive pathways that guide the design of improved accessibility. A project that exploits the potential offered by technological innovation and implements multimedia, virtual and augmented reality, video mapping, artificial intelligence, gamification, 3D printing and media arts for a participatory experience of places and memories.

The aim of this research is to propose a new interpretive framework that attempts to address the contemporary need for design solutions related to architecture and its context that support not only physical accessibility, but also sensory-perceptual-cognitive and digital accessibility aimed at a wide range of users.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Accessibility, be it physical, cognitive, emotional, digital or cultural, is now an essential concept for a society that wants to call itself modern. In addition to this important qualitative dimension, there is also a quantitative one, which implies a development model aimed at making our cultural heritage not only an expression of our national identity, but also a driving force for sustainable development, closely linked to the tourism sector. From this point of view, accessibility is an important indicator of the welcome and quality of the cultural experience, embodying the right to culture mentioned above.

This research project aims to engage in a stimulating and constantly evolving field of reflection, particularly in the light of the setback of the health emergency and the post-pandemic recovery of the culture and tourism sectors, which have been particularly affected. The aim is to contribute to sector-specific scientific research and to promote a new culture of cooperation and synergy between public and private bodies.

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